

Comparative Aesthetic Analysis of Two female Monograph by Mir Afzal Tuni and Mirza Baba

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Abstract

With the arrival of the Europeans and the effects of Western style on Safavid painting, women's images, which had previously been viewed as a complementary feature, began to appear separately and individually in single-leaf illustration of the Isfahan school. This process continued until the first half of the Qajar school. In fact, the introduction of new art materials, as well as the change in government and regional relocation from Isfahan to Tehran, influenced the show of single figures. The two monographs, "A reclining woman and her lapdog" by Mir Afzal Tuni from Isfahan School and "Qajar Lady" by Mirza Baba from court paintings of the first half of Qajar School, are the examples studied in this article. The aim is to study the visual structure and comparative aesthetic analysis of these two works, which examines the differences and similarities in the seductive representation of the female monograph. Despite having different techniques and cultures in performing an emerging subject such as monographs, the findings indicate that both artists appeared to show the intellectual spaces of life in the palace as well as the corruption and destruction in their society.

Keywords

Nudism, Female monograph, Isfahan school single-leaf Illustration, Mir Afzal Tuni, Mirza Baba, Qajar court painting

Introduction

The portrayal of a woman as an object in art has a strong presence, and her physical body has been used numerous times because of her aesthetic ability. The monograph of women started in the late Safavid period, during Reza Abbasi's reign and the infiltration of Western aesthetics in the portrayal of women, and continued in a new form until the Qajar era. The single-leaf illustration demonstrates a reduction in exposure to space and an emphasis on the body as the main topic. In reality, the patrons of these works did not want women to be recognized and illustrated on the same level as other people. Accordingly, the degree of accuracy in the performing of details and clothing and figure increased significantly. Centered on an aesthetic approach, this paper attempts to describe and analyze a work by Mir Afzal Tuni and a work by Mirza Baba. Mir Afzal Tuni, one of the painters of the reign of Shah Abbas II, represent the monograph of a woman who is leaning on a pillow and watching a tiny and cute dog next to her. In contrast, Mirza Baba, a painter from the Fath-Ali Shah Qajar period, portrays a single figure of a woman sitting on a carpet with an apple in

her right hand and a cup in her left hand for drinking. Despite the fact that the two paintings are very different in terms of time and history, technique, and even size, they share specific and similar characteristics. Whether in representing the appearance of the figures or in interpreting the subtle aesthetic distinctions. Accordingly, the first section will provide explanations about the general characteristics of women painted in Isfahan schools and court paintings of the Qajar school with a focus on the aspect of nudism, followed by introductions to two famous artists of the period. In case of the studied subject in this paper, no research has been carried out with the nudism approach thus far, in the meantime we can only mention the article of Mina Mohammadi Vakil and Hasan (2014) titled "From Prohibition of Portraiture to Naked Pictography* A Brief Review of the Evolution of Human Figure Representation in the History of Art especially Iran" to study the approach of different religions on human representation, contradiction and contradiction in the meaning of nudity and the duality of the meaning of this concept is examined terminologically, then with a closer look at Iranian art changes the attitude of the Qajar era artist towards human images. Ashley Mayer Burns (2016) in her dissertation "The Development of the Seated Female Nude in Seventeenth-century Safavid Painting" examined a small group of single-sheet and Murals of seated semi-nude lady type from Isfahan to find out why and how this motif become tailored to Persian painters' repertoire.

Methodology

This article uses a qualitative method that is focused on historical and descriptive-analytical study with an aesthetic approach. Two drawings were chosen as a case study and representative of the Isfahan and Qajar schools due to their thematic similarity. The data will then be compared using the comparative studies approach. To achieve the research's objectives, structural analysis of how each individual female monograph fits into the overall composition, as well as color, symbolism, and morphology (Face processing system, limb processing, clothing and decorations) will be carried out using picture tables. Finally, the findings will be presented, along with a description of the commonalities and differences in this field. The data was gathered through library and documentary study of a variety of written sources.

The aesthetics of painting a woman's figure in Isfahan school

Isfahan school paintings are full of figures of women in different settings, often alone or next to one or more beautiful young people. As a result, the works of this period have very distinct and internal states that are distinct from previous compositions. There are often factors of nature in the background of women's status that serve only to harmonize the work's negative space with the painting's subject. Oleg Grabar (2000) emphasizes the importance of portraiture and the emergence of new perspectives focused on artists' individuality and he claims "We see artists who become real artists independent of the royal workshops during the Safavid era. Artists with unique backgrounds and private lives that seem to be mirrored in their work. These artists have lived among the community's people, and has helped to broaden the social base of artists and, as a result, the number of people who value visual art." Therefore, the gradual change in artistic thought at the time caused the special taste of the time, which preferred fat and large limbs, manifested itself in the creation of women's figures. (Yasini 2013)

Nudism in Isfahan School Single-Leaf Illustration

There are paintings of women in special circumstances with sensual states in some parts of Isfahan school single-leaf illustration that have only taken on an ornamental role and are created for the pleasure of the eye. In reality, depicting nude and semi-naked bodies and highlighting feminine elements by Iranian artists shows attention to the material components and themes of social life in the same way as many Europeans' works does. It seems that in a society like the Safavid era, despite being so-called Islamic, it has acted relatively culturally in some areas. The wealthy prostitutes described in the French traveler and businessman Georges Jean Chardin's travelogue are among them. Those that, in his opinion (1830), wore expensive clothing and jewelry, as well as popular make-up at the time. "The brothel girls were more beautiful and attractive than the Circassian prisoners and Georgians." There was a prostitute neighborhood in Isfahan known as the nude or unveiled alley. These places were built after the establishment of independent governments in Iran, according to Ravandi (1990) in his book *Social History of Iran*, to maintain the status of families and provide security for ordinary girls and women in cities, because if there is no place for men to spend time and have fun, they turn to chaste girls. For this reason, they were given a location outside of the city where the soldiers and men could have fun without disturbing other women.

The condition of prostitution is also depicted in the report of German tourist Engelbert Kaempfer (1940), who reveals the freedom of action and the open participation of women in public. For prostitutes who did not work in the infamous district, Shah Square was one of the most popular locations. They were allowed to stay in the square itself in addition to the rented rooms on the upper floors surrounding Shah Square too. According to Chardin, the square was covered with numerous tents set up by prostitutes at night, so that the Taliban could "choose the woman they wanted in these tents." (Chardin 1830) Surprisingly, the tax was changing to the extent of beauty and charm. As an anonymous Venetian merchant who visited Iran in 1673 explains and admits: "Prostitutes who commute in public areas pay taxes based on their attractiveness; the more attractive they are, the higher the taxes they would pay..." (Barbaro et al 1873) Moreover, prostitutes had a significant social status in the Safavid era. Because, apart from economic interests, they played a minor role in the politico-military body owing to their association with the war corps. This is confirmed by the following explanation from D.Garcia de Silva Figueroa (1667), the Spanish ambassador to the Safavid court, in his travelogue: "Soldiers were usually sent on war trips with prostitutes to reinforce them by dancing, singing, and fulfilling their sexual needs; without them, the army would not have survived on the front lines."

Another interesting thing about these women was their religious activity. According to Figueroa, these women attended the mourning service in the following way: There are narrow porticos belonging to woman of craftsmen and wholesalers in the mosque's courtyard, and part of the porches belong to prostitutes, who are generally treated with greater reverence since the king profits from them. These women are easily identifiable because they have a larger crew and usually ride horses; they dress better and, unlike other women, do not wear black chador¹ or yellow and brown ones. Instead, they dress in full silk gowns and chador made of delicate embroidered fabrics, and most of them sit with their faces uncovered². They are always well-dressed and well-behaved. The interesting thing was that at the end of the mourning ceremony, these high-level prostitutes approached the men

with shame and modesty while holding a small wooden box or gold box and without saying a word, they stand to be given alms. They send these alms to those that they have already recognized as being in need. As a result, prostitutes were so well-known that they were often given a special spot in religious mourning rituals. But prostitution in Isfahan did not stop there; it seems that there was another community of ordinary citizens who were compelled to do so by their husbands' greed and selfishness. Some of the dancers and singers listed in Figueroa's report belonged to this community (Those who were seen at the celebrations of officials and were paid depending on what they did) (Silva Figueroa 1667)

As previously stated, unique historical and social circumstances in the late Safavid era influenced the morality that has made female prostitution so widespread in Iranian society. This has a clear impact on the remaining paintings from that time period. "The design of women's bodies was always covered, which demonstrated chastity and modesty while also making women inaccessible, but to some extent, following Western designs, some exaggerations were performed in the proportions of the limbs and the way dealt with their physical appearance." This trend changed the taste of Iranian art, and the dressed and chaste picture of women in miniature painting sometimes turned into works of semi-naked or naked women who in the age of glory and "The greatness of Iranian painting has been unprecedented. (Yasini 2013) Thus, during the reigns of Shah Safi I and Shah Abbas II, the proliferation of nude paintings of semi-lustful subjects can be attributed to moral corruption and public welfare. However, such subjects were not possible to spread without Iranian art masters' acquaintance with European block printing. (Javani 2011) "This art is non-spiritual and requires a viewer seeking aesthetics rather than meaning," Anthony Welch believes late Safavid painting has declined. (Welch 1974)

The identity of erotic women painted in the schools of Isfahan is such that it can be designed in a way that does not appear in the outside world and does not belong to a specific person. Hence, they are completely unknown and may not exist at all. However, since the women of the court and the harem, as well as the noblewomen, had a privileged status and could not leave the house without a chador to avoid being seen by the men, it was not appropriate for them to be shown nude. By examining historical documents such as travelogues and linking them to paintings, it is possible to infer that these pictures were associated with the wealthy prostitutes of the time, which strictly appeared on the sexy body as an ever-present and also unmasked commodity and face covering as a new subject in the form and composition of the painting page.

Mir Afzal Tuni

Afzal al-Husayni, also known as Mir Afzal Tuni, was a painter in Shah Abbas II's court and also one of Reza Abbasi's students, whose works date from 1049 to 1061 AH. He was active in both book design and drawing single-leaf figures in a variety of styles. His subjects are young people in love, which he often depicted nude, in vibrant colors and gold. (Azhand 2014) Moonlight white faces, almond-shaped eyes, and woven upwards brows can also be identified in his works owing to the use of darker brown and blue colors. His other favorite decorative features are the role of porcelain vases in blue and white colors. Despite the fact that Afzal was a unique artist and a meticulous painter, his pen occasionally trembled, and some of his works are strikingly similar to Reza's style. (Soudavar 1992)

Figure 2. *Young Portuguese Man*. (1634) by Reza Abbasi. 14.6 x 19.2 cm. Detroit Institute of Arts

Figure 1. *A reclining woman and her lapdog* (1640) by Mir Afzal Tuni. 15.8* 11.9. British Museum. London. United Kingdom

Visual analysis and description of the "A reclining woman and her lapdog"

One of Afzal's signature works is the single-leaf illustration "A reclining woman and her lapdog" (Figure 1), dating to 1050 AH, now housed in the British Museum in London. He has signed his miniature painting with the text of "Mir Afzal Tuni" in Nastaliq script on the upper abdomen of the woman. This painting is done in the style and context of Reza Abbasi, and it accurately represents his standards. (Pope 1964) It is in keeping with the Isfahan school in terms of composition, concept, implementation, and payment. This painting has been wrongly attributed to Reza Abbasi because he also has a painting of the same theme. A European Portuguese is watching a dog which is licking a glass of wine, not a beautiful young lady, as seen in the young Portuguese painting (Figure 2). Furthermore, Reza Abbasi depicts a half-naked woman as a drunk, rather than a sober woman who, by removing her shirt, reveals her underwear and a portion of her naked body. (Canby 1993) Reza's paintings are often more dynamic than Afzal's, as Afzal's art style and compositions are usually constant and static. "The moonlight white color of the face, the arched eyebrows painted above the almond eyes and the fat hands protruding from the ends of the sleeves are the characteristics that Mir Afzal has learned from Reza." (Soudavar 1992) Many of the landscape elements in this scene, such as the large golden leaves, palm-shaped tree, tall, wavy grass, and twisted and windy clouds, are all part of his master's unique landscape making features.

In Mir Afzal's painting, a beautiful woman is depicted leaning on her bed, watching the lapdog pose in a hollow bowl. In the Mir Afzal painting, a beautiful woman is leaning on her bed, watching the lapdog pose licking a bowl. In reality, the woman has been portrayed in such a way that she occupies the entire picture, while the dog has been portrayed as a supplement and secondary character. In the image of the relaxed state of the woman, the clothes, the hair and the free behavior of the dog, induce a kind of comfort and relaxation³. A golden plate, a cup, and a few fruits can be seen at the bottom of the frame, and an expensive porcelain vase with a bunch of pink roses can be seen at the end of the figure. The decorative motifs and patterns used in the body of the vase are adapted from Chinese landscape trees with two levels of blue and azure paint on a layer of white glaze. To

emphasize the colors and shapes of the figure, a monochrome background has been created. Delicate folds on the clothes are visible on the wrists, elbows, underarms and between the legs. Other features of the figure are the delicacy of the hands, fingers, and especially the head and facial features, as well as long black braided hair, which is cast in the form of wavy lines on the face, shoulders and background. In contrast to the large thighs, the fat belly and the oval face have somewhat reduced its feminine elegance. The structure of the work, like other single-leaf of this period, remains Iranian and traditional. One of the unique aspects of Iranian clothing is the style of clothing worn by women, especially their patterned underwear. Trees and surroundings also resemble Iranian paintings in shape and type. However, it has been influenced by Western culture and thought in certain aspects, such as the presence of an animal and nudity. In reality, "the picture of small dogs in paintings from that era was a foreign souvenir that became common in works with the rise of European block printing. In this picture, the dog is licking a bowl that does not seem to be for animal food and is actually a glass for wine." (Tavallayi 2014)

Fadavi (2007) refers to this ethical breaking late Safavid artists' customs, such as revealing the bare stomach and carnal states of the body, in his book, but he changes the cup of wine to a bowl of water. The point to consider is that the woman folded up a corner of her loose, long shirt and exposes a part of her body to the viewer, which indicates her seduction. According to the book of Art of the Persian courts, "youth" and "drunkenness" have been subjects of interest to Iranians. (Soudavar 1992) Perhaps the artist has completely exposed the woman's abdomen and navel in order to satisfy the client's request to show nudity. Tahvilian (2008) explains "Women used to fold up a portion of their shirts to show off their underwear and contribute to the charm of their clothing,". But so much uplifting is undoubtedly erotic. This hypothesis seems certain when the open collar of the dress and the flirtatious and provocative mood of the woman are added to it. (Tavallayi 2014) Also, the abandoned wrinkled shawl of flows between the legs and the elongated shape of the feverish body of the woman, like a river flowing in the bed of a sheet of paper, further defines her drunkenness. A branch with a few white flowers can be seen in the center of her chest, which emerges from the dress's slit and can be interpreted as a sign of love flirtation.

According to experts from the British Museum, this piece most certainly portrays a prostitute with valuable pottery, cushions, and vivid garments; it tells of his lavish lifestyle and high earnings. While being fully dressed, the woman looks like a prostitute⁴. According to the book "Masterpieces from the Department of Islamic Art in the Metropolitan Museum of Art," wealth and prostitution enabled high-level prostitutes to dress with taste for aristocratic clients and high-ranking officers during the Safavid rule in the seventeenth century. Men who could afford such decent prostitutes. This image is in common with other images of that time. (Layla 1998) Thomas Herbert (1929) describes prostitutes' clothing "Their dresses are loose and glittering, reaching down to their ankles; and underneath, they wear satin or costly embroideries trousers." Then he adds details including braided and fragrant hair, oriental pearl pendants on the cheeks, jeweled pigeons around the neck, ear rings, flowers or a turquoise-colored piece of gold on the nose, ruby and sapphire or other precious stones.

Figure 3. *A reclining woman and her lapdog* (1640) by Mir Afzal Tuni. part of the work

The aesthetics of painting a woman's figure in Qajar school

The paintings of the first Qajar era depict an unrealistic picture of the grandeur and dignity of court women, who are depicted according to the rules of ideal beauty of the time, which are very different from today's standards. Faces in this rule have a kind of characterization with the same characteristics prevails in the faces. Women's faces are generally round, and their brows are attached and have a mole on their face. Some of the most typical characteristics of a woman's face in a pictorial painting are hangover eyes, a half-open mouth, a small mouth, and a red lip, as well as a narrow nose. (Jahangard et al 2015). According to Rahnavard (2007), "the artist painter at this time has given further attention to the subject's visual and objective influences... bending the head to one side and a feminine elegance with prominent breasts, fat buttocks, strings of pearls and woman's jewels, as well as having hennas on hands have become characteristic of court women". The paintings' scenic patterns are based on the architecture of the palaces and are very similar to the court. A vision of nature or architecture can be seen in the background of some scenes. (Pakbaz 2006) The decorative nature is also evident in the coloring and design. The contractual nature of the figures in this school does not go beyond a few categories; women dancers, acrobats, musicians, mothers with children-primarily inspired by the figure of Mary in European art. There are several such instances in which a woman and a man are sitting next to each other as lovers. (Jahangard et al 2015)

Nudism in Qajar School Single-Leaf Illustration

Given that depictions of nude women with bare breasts or women whose bodies are apparent due to the silk of their clothes make up a significant portion of Qajar court iconography, the following topic focuses on Fath Ali Shah's womanizer and his influence on the court's artistic orders.

Having a royal harem was one of the Shah's favorite pastimes. Women in the Qajar court had an erotic source that was exclusive to the Shah. In reality, prostitution started in the court itself. Azod Al-Duleh (1997) claims in his memoirs that despite having a thousand wives and concubines, he did not hesitate to welcome and even house Tehran's musicians, artists, actors, and female singers to his palace. With Daf⁵, tar, fiddle, dulcimer, and Tombak⁶, these seductive women introduced all of the possible entertaining arts to the royal palace with beauty and charm, and transformed the king's palace into a center of human desires.

Fath Ali Shah, who had a great desire for women, tried to have them in his shrine. Madame Jane Dieulafoy (1989) writes to show the condition of the harem and the extent of his immorality and promiscuity: "In this hall, the king was having odd entertainment. The harem's naked ladies climbed the sloping surface and sat at the top of the slide, releasing themselves to slide into a pool of water and amusing the king. Another of his hobbies is said to have been to spread a cloth, pour some shredded silk thread on it, and order his numerous wives to walk on it barefoot. As a result, the hard and soft legs were separated, and those who did not have a piece of silk attached to their feet were rewarded." It is clear from this that corruption and debauchery within such a large harem have given rise to the king's mental inclination to order and see the erotic images of women by the court painters of this era. In reality, the state of culture in Fath Ali Shah's court demonstrates a focus on physical aspects as well as the use of women as a dramatic instrument in court iconography of the time.

Another genre of Iranian paintings uses a collection of figures and a general design theme, as well as great talent and imagination, but their subjects are so offensive that they irritate the viewer's eyes. "Some of the figures were painted on canvas and had the proportions of a true human being, giving the rich's shrine a new charm." (Floor 2002) Another significant factor in the proliferation of nudity in the Qajar era has been attributed to the widespread influence of Western art and the effects of familiarity with the academic current of humanism⁷. Newly discovered humanistic ideas increasingly expressed in the aesthetic material of works of art, including emotional and sexual images, or, in this age's parlance, pornography. Although the number of these images remains small, some researchers have attributed the disappearance of such images in the coming years to their inconsistency with social traditions. However, it is possible to consider the existence of such photographs during the Qajar era by consulting the documents. (Mohammadi Vakil 2014)

James Baillie Fraser (1973) referred to the paintings of the house of "Mirza Abul Hassan Khan Ilchi". In his opinion, the worst part of the room was the paintings that made a nasty attempt to depict beauties naked or in low clothes, with terribly blushed cheeks, eyes that had been fatally blackened, eyebrows like the ebony tree bow and all the moods and behaviors showed too much beauty and charm⁸. Also, other people such as Charles James Wills, Tancoigne, Ouseley have documented the prevalence of erotic images in the Qajar era. Therefore, it is based on a multitude of such documents and evidences that we can take a closer look at the erotic paintings of harem women in terms of their cultural and psychological importance and role. Among them are the Shah's and the aristocracy's desire to see such issues, as well as the copying of European art, the training of Iranian artists in the West, and the deterioration of religious teachings. (Floor 2002)

Mirza Baba Shirazi

Mirza Baba was the first painter in the Qajar court. Despite his ability to paint in a variety of styles, he was responsible for the spread of oil painting and the Qajar court icon painting style in Iran. Mirza Baba's works indicate that he was active as an artist between 1200 and 1245 AH. He was most likely a pupil of Agha Sadiq, also known as Mohammad Sadiq. Because in some of his paintings he has used a style similar to Mohammad Sadiq. (Azhand 2007) He was from Shiraz, and before passing power to the Qajar dynasty, he served for Karim Khan Zand. (Dadvar 2005). The faces of princes and courtiers, the faces of dancing and singer girls with hangover eyes, romantic lovers, and still life are among the subjects of her oil paintings. Since he had acquired the title of "painter" from Fath Ali Shah at the time, he demonstrated his modesty by adding the sentence (the least Mirza Baba) in the beautiful calligraphy of Nastaliq. In the simulation, the face painting and decoration of the clothes was precise and delicate, and he used the colors in a balanced and harmonious way (Shafizadeh & Rajabi 2008) And all in all, he used mixed and somewhat dark colors. He painted faces that were beautiful and natural, and in some cases unobtrusive and shy, and eyes that were hangover, often looking to the right. Karimzadeh Tabrizi (1997) describes him as a patient and obsessive designer, writing about how he performs flower and fabric arrangements: This artist reportedly used special molds in the design of flowers and other fabric decorations, and he adjusted the flower design with molds in order to cover the whole surface of the garment with standard and uniform decorations and flower arrangements, and even His master pupil, Mihr 'Ali, has used these techniques. However, he had many flaws in the rules of perspective, and in some situations, he applied the perspective accurately, but he was completely unaware of the significance of the essence of the matter.

Figure 4. *the Qajar Lady* (1800) by Mirza Baba. 146*94 cm. Oil paint and metal sheet on canvas. British Museum. London. United Kingdom.

Figure 5. *Lady playing the Setar* 1769-70) by Moahammad Sadiq (Shiraz, private collection. Oil paint

Visual analysis and description of the "The Qajar Lady"

One of Mirza Baba's outstanding paintings is an oil painting in which the portrait of a Qajar lady is depicted. He has signed his painting by adding the sentence (the least Mirza Baba) in Shekasteh Nastaliq's beautiful calligraphy on the right and the middle of the picture. (Figure4) This painting, which is in the British Museum, belongs to the first half of the Qajar school. Mirza Baba has learned greatly from his teacher Mohammad Sadiq's style in this painting. This master pupil's composition is strikingly similar to Mohammad Sadiq's painting "Lady playing the Setar" (Figure5) from 1182-83 AH, which bears the signature "Ya Sadih Al-Wahd" and has been copied from it. (Diba & Ekhtiar1998). An inspection of the present painting reveals that the woman's gesture and posture are identical in both works. Legs were crossed, soles of feet were hennaed, and hands and arms were painted exactly the same. Instead of an instrument, Mirza Baba used an apple in her right hand and a glass of wine in her left. The status of the left hand on the left knee, as well as the fingers on both hands, are exact replicas of Mohammad Sadiq's original drawing. So that, if we place the instrument in the hands of Mirza Baba's figure as it is in the hands of Mohammad Sadiq's figure, she will be able to play as well. Clothes and environments are almost identical. Even the openness of the slit of the silk dress is the same. In addition, the wine bottle at the bottom left of the image, the glamorous carpet, and the geometric railing are all structurally similar. (Diba & Ekhtiar1998)

The sitting Qajar lady in Mirza Baba's painting is dressed in the manner of court ladies, with make-up, clothing, and ornaments. She is looking outside the curtain with a special gesture and an oval face that is vertically on a cylindrical neck. A few things can be discussed briefly. First and foremost, the lady has henna on the soles and palms of her hands and feet. Henna is a symbol of heaven, peace, love, and good fortune, according to the ancient Iranians, and it was a popular practice among Qajar women. As a result, Mirza Baba was most likely attempting to portray the joy of a Qajar lady. Another is that the painter, in order to emphasize the monograph, covers half of the background with simple composition and muted colors so that the female face sits beautifully in the eyes of the audience. And the other half, with the dominance of warm colors, is composed of a patterned carpet spread out under the foot of the figure and a geometric plinth. The artist's realism-based oil painting skill can be seen in the clothes and decorations on it, as well as in the drawing of jewelry.

In addition, both Eastern and Western attitudes can be seen in the work simultaneously. In the one side, there is the artist's Eastern subjectivism, which is manifested in the artist's simplification of elements and forms and the depiction of the carpet from above. In the other hand, shading of components and objects based on the ideals of realism in Western art is apparent, such as the shadow of the foot on the carpet and the shadow of the crystal on the ground. Mirza Baba expertly painted the net dress to fit the woman's body protrusions, and the silk is so thin that the woman's body and part of her underwear can be seen plainly. (Figure6) Red apples and wine glasses that show off in a woman's hands have been

used as symbolic concepts of love, sexual desire and breeding. The issue of light is also a complex issue in this painting, so that the gentle lighting was used to show the volume of elements and shapes. This kind of light radiation, on the other hand, has given the work a sense of weightlessness. This work focuses on the simulation of natural textures of items such as glass and glassware, carpet texture, wood and cloth, all of which have a naturalistic visual framework. Also, natural colors that belong to the elements and objects have been used for composition and color unity. The vertical bust is balanced with all the weight in the background thanks to the yellow or ochre horizontal line just over the wooden plinth and its color harmony with the thin strip of carpet. Also, it should not be forgotten that this tableau has been cut around to be installed in a specific and desired place. Thus, the painting frame can be considered as one of its aesthetic characteristics, because its practical reason has created a new form in the painter's work. (Jalali Jafari 2003)

Figure 6. Figure 4. *the Qajar Lady* (1800) by Mirza Baba. Part of the work

A person like Madame Carla Serena was one of the few women writers and tourists who, alone due to her innate feminine curiosity, was able to access the Andarunis⁹ of Iranian women and their banquets. Describing the home clothes of Qajar women, she said: "Iranian women's clothing at home, as everyone knows, is very showy and luxurious. A garment made of thin netting and embroidered with hand using motifs and precious stones covered the upper body. This thin covering is completed with a few pieces of jewelry..." (Serena 1883) (Figure6)

A Comparative Aesthetic Analysis of the "A reclining woman and her lapdog " by Mir Afzal Tuni and "The Qajar Lady" by Mirza Baba

By analyzing and citing all that was stated in the previous sections, we can briefly show the aesthetic components of the two works in the form of image tables No. 1, 2 and 3, then perform a comparative analysis of the information within it.

Data Analysis Table 1

The following outcomes were derived through the comparative aesthetic appearance (face and body) of the two paintings:

Mir Afazl Tuni's painting avoids realistic portrayal of female bodies, favoring Iranian almond shapes and hungover eyes over bevel and Mongolian eyes. Furthermore, the interior states of the figure may be noticed through alterations in the arms and legs, the body's inclination to curve, and obesity and largeness in particular organs; As a result, a woman's face reflects her spiritual energy and has less color and glaze. The use of pure colors and the absence of perspective in painting has also resulted in the formation of a world of youth, freshness, and vivacity. In contrast, the female body in Mirza Baba's painting is quite physically defined, and there is no attempt to convey psychological aspects in the face; as a result, it impresses itself on the viewer and has assumed a formal and dramatic form. Regardless of the characterization, the components of the face have been completed with a few soft and delicate colors, and exaggeration has been done to highlight the details more elegantly; such as the form of the lips that are closer to the real state, or the eyes that are bigger and more natural, and the brows that are much broader.

As a result, the practice of painting and glazing a woman's face has been utilized to increase her lustfulness. Another is that Mirza Baba's painting has a multidimensional effect due to the combination of two horizontal angles to display the legs and a three-dimensional angle to display the face. The arms and legs are also made in an ancient and even more clumsy way. However, none of the single figures are looking at the viewer, and their gaze is fixated on points that do not appear to be in this world and that they are observing in their imagination. The faces are shown at such an angle that they constantly imply the existence of an absent lover (visual complement) beyond the frame. The figures are immobile and in a condition of passivity, tranquility, and quiet. The women's lips are closed, and they are pleased with an imperceptible smile. Maybe both painters sought to create the most beautiful human face possible, with closed lips.

Table 1. Matching the two artworks in terms of physical appearance (Source: Authors)

Physical Appearance in Single-leaf Painting of "A reclining woman and her lapdog" by Mir Afzal Tuni			
Sample picture			
Face	<p>Round face & chin dimple Narrow and small mouth Puffy almond-shaped eyes, oblique & black eyes Thin crescent-shaped eyebrows not too full and twisted upwards A delicate nose with a fine line and a slightly broad tip Long and braided hair, with a wavy hair strand around the ears and face.</p>		
Body	<p>Fat limbs with a protruding navel and a big abdomen Long and gathered neck Hands are plump and hooked, with oval arms Fingers are smaller & thinner than the rest of the body Thighs are thick, the foot is smaller and thinner than the rest of the body, and the right foot is behind the left foot. Moonlight pink is the hue of her skin.</p>		
Physical Appearance in Single-leaf Painting of "Qajar Lady" by Mirza Baba			
Sample picture			
Face	<p>Spherical chin, three-quarters face, round, long forehead, red cheeks Brown & hangover eyes that have been blackened with kohl Broad and arched brows, and a tattoo between the brows The nose is long and narrow, and it cuts the face in half The mouth is small & striking The hair on the front of the head is curled to the cheekbones and descends from both sides to near the brows</p>		
Body	<p>Tall and coarse limb, wide shoulders & a swollen belly Umbilicus and chest are small and round Head-to-body ratio is small Hands with henna on them Neck is long and broad feet with henna on them The feet's soles are smaller and more delicate than the rest of the body. The skin color is wheat white (body color is lighter)</p>		

Table 2. Matching the two artworks in terms of the clothing and ornament (Source: Authors)

Clothing and ornaments in Single-leaf Painting of "A reclining woman and her lapdog" by Mir Afzal Tuni			
Sample picture			
Clothing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long green underwear with a button on the collar - Blue cloak with long and tight sleeves that are connected at the front with straps - Light cream-colored waist scarf abandoned between the legs - white Tights with golden floral patterns and blue thread folded at the waist 		
Headdress	A long orange shawl that extends from the back to the ground		
Footwear	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leggings (a band that wraps around the leg) long up to the knee and decorated with gold arabesque straps on a light and dark blue fabric background - Barefoot 		
Jewelry	Long gold earrings, a necklace consisting of delicate and colorful gems, a thin ring with two blue diamonds and gold jewels on the nose		
Clothing and ornaments in Single-leaf Painting of "Qajar Lady" by Mirza Baba			
Sample picture			
Clothing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thin white silk shirt with a slit opened from the front and embroidered with crochet and fastened with a button on the collar - Arkhaliq¹⁰ (upper torso) with slots and sword sleeves and embroidery on the arm- Pattern of fabric from narrow striped designs in two colors, white and crimson, vertically and diagonally, each way is decorated with a repetition of small floral patterns in the middle. - Loose and long pants made of velvet (decorated with traditional arabesque patterns such as Khorasani style gilding (small geometric patterns), Paisley of Termeh¹¹, Mohammadi flowers and buds, and colorful and fine roses and leaves. 		
Headdress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A hat with a string of pearls tied to it and going under the chin, embellished with multiple miniature repeating flowers on a white and brown stripe. - A long orange shawl with a huge floral border that repeats. 		
Footwear	Barefoot		
Jewelry	Earrings, head clips, bracelets and brooches decorated with pearls and jewelry		

Data Analysis Table 2

The following was determined based on the received table and a comparative aesthetic analysis of the cover and ornaments of these two works:

In the style of Mir Afzal art, there is not much make-up and decorations and the figure is portrayed with a long, loose and comfortable shirt. As there are so many layers of clothing, the underlying fabrics can only be distinguished from collar or sleeve cuts that vary in color. The woman's dress is embellished with a wavy shawl and a pleated shirt with rhythmic twists, creating a proportion with all of the work's components. The original compositions and patterns of porcelain clouds (spiral clouds) and smooth and delicate Islamic patterns of flowers and plants are the major types of tunic decoration. On the other hand, the arts of embroidery, engraving, and embellishment played a significant part in the decoration of Qajar lady clothes in Mirza Baba painting. The lady is dressed in a high-quality velvet and silk cloth of few and thin layers. The text of the fabric and the style of the decoration show a frequent and almost exclusive use of the motifs of flowers, flower petals, and large and small repeated leaves; all of this suggests that this sort of decoration belonged to the glorious clothes of the women of the harem or were used more there and originated from the tastes of the Andaruni tailors. The excessive use of royal jewels represents the material well-being of court women in comparison to the rest of the region.

In the other hand, Qajar women's sense of modernity had become so strong that the painter was interested in wearing European thin clothes for women. The head covering remains the same as it was before (Zand dynasty). Another notable characteristic in women's clothing is the use of perspective science to display the wide folds and folds of fabrics and to offer symmetrical designs and patterns based on illustrations from the eighteenth-century French. Another thing to consider is that, although both figures' dresses are luxurious, they don't cover the whole body. Because of the influence of Western art, portions of their bodies can be seen by thin silk or the folding of a top to show off feminine limbs such as bare breasts, navel, and belly.

Conclusion

Despite technical changes and the use of various materials and tools in the performance of the two works, a kind of connection was found in the content of Mir Afzal Toni's painting with Mirza Baba's painting.

The identity of the depicted women is unknown. Only by depending on the signs in the paintings and comparing them with historical records and travelogues may we conclude that Mirza Baba's figure was most likely a court musician or entertainer. and she is portrayed imaginatively rather than with a real face. And the woman in Mir Afzal Tuni's painting is most likely a prostitute who, based on her half-naked body and lazy lethargy, is dissatisfied with her status as a prostitute. Perhaps the socioeconomic circumstances of Isfahan society, economic prosperity, and the government's trade and cultural ties with Western nations are all factors in demonstrating power and a need to focus on women. It

should be remembered that the process of "A reclining woman and her lapdog" function is related to the outer room, indicating that it is not reliant on the court. It is as if the artist has portrayed a part of a beautiful woman without her knowledge.

However, in the case of Mirza Baba's single figure, the woman has attempted to preserve her extreme integrity and sobriety despite her thin covering, which was attributed not only to the character of her courtly aristocracy, but also to the nationality and race of Qajar women of Turkish descent. The "Qajar Lady" seems to have been set in front of the painter's eyes as an order, as she is depicted in a humble and obedient state, with an artificial and ritual gesture in the interior of the palace.

According to the documents, moreover, both artists emulated their masters in their content and composition, indicating excellence in drawing, nurturing talent, and fulfilling the sense of beauty, and justifying the teacher-student partnership. In general, the appearance of a puppy, the show of valuable ornaments and jewels, ornate handmade garments, luxuries and lavish decorations of the environment all reflect both women's high wealth and social status. As a result, both works vividly represent the socio-cultural condition of the period, as well as the influence of European style.

Table 3. Comparative aesthetic analysis of the commonalities and differentiations of two monographs from Mir Afzal Tuni and Mirza Baba (source: Authors)

	The commonalities of two single-leaf figures	
	Mir Afzal Tuni Painting	Mirza Baba Painting
Topic	The monograph of a woman influenced by the painting "Young Portuguese" by Reza Abbasi	The monograph of a woman influenced by the painting "Lady playing the Setar" by Mohammad Sadiq
Visual Signs	The two-dimensional space is filled with aristocratic daily objects such as crystal goblets, fruits, vases, bowls and plates, as well as couches, carpets, and rugs	
Decoration	Using ornamental patterns and motifs in clothing, as well as combining ornamental and visual themes like gold and jewelry.	
Imitation of European painting	appropriation of European visual symbols such as dogs and monographs	Eclecticism of Western methods such as using oil paint for volume, light shadow, fading colors and perspective
Signature	Nastaliq	Shekasteh Nastaliq
Nudity	Drawing erotic scenes from semi-nude figures to emphasize feminine characteristics	
Clothes	Realism in clothing and drawing special samples of Iranian dress, especially pants, showing tight and thin clothes, not using footwear	
	The Differentiations of Two Single-leaf Figures	
	Mir Afzal Tuni Painting	Mirza Baba Painting
Method	Inks, opaque watercolors and gold on paper	Oil paint on canvas (linen)
color	Colors are varied, flat, and brilliant (Gold, blue, green, orange, white, crimson and cream)	Limited color selection with a predominance of warm colors (red, orange, Sangria, brown and dark blue)
Composition	The image has a horizontal rectangular frame with a calligraphic border, a diagonal composition, and the figure is buoyant.	Vertical rectangular frame, upper side of arched effect - structural symmetry and replacement of the figure in the middle of the image
Space & Background	Open environment with patches of twisting clouds, trees and shrubs	Taken from the interior of the palace
Dimensions	11.7 × 16 cm	94 × 146 cm
Light	Lack of focused light source	External light source and from the left of the image
Style	Realistic The figure is on the right side of the image and is looking to the right	Naturalistic, embellished and conventional The figure is on the left side of the image and is looking to the right
Usage	included in albums belonging to members of the royal family or the nobility, or maybe for selling to members of the lower classes	Decorating the royal palace and the halls of wealthy families' homes, and catering to the king's and court's tastes

Postscript

- 1- It is an outer garment or open cloak worn by many women in public settings or outdoors in Iran, Iraq, and other nations within the Persianate cultural domain, as well as predominately Shia areas.
- 2- Prostitutes at the time did not hide their faces, which was considered unpleasant. Ravandi (1990) was quoted as saying by John Cartwright, "Such women did not normally wear masks."
- 3- Google arts & culture. <https://artsandculture.google.com/asset/mir-afzal-of-tun-a-reclining-woman-and-her-lapdog-a-painting/6wHmPb2BEdBj8g> (Retrieved September 2, 2020)
- 4- Google arts & culture. <https://artsandculture.google.com/asset/mir-afzal-of-tun-a-reclining-woman-and-her-lapdog-a-painting/6wHmPb2BEdBj8g> (Retrieved September 2, 2020)
- 5- The Daf is a frame drum from the Middle East (mostly Iran) that is utilized in popular and traditional music in Iran and Pakistan.
- 6- An Iranian goblet drum known as the tombak, tonbak, or zarb. It is the most important percussion instrument in Persian music.
- 7- The importance of thinking, according to this approach, is characterized not by the holy man's relationship to the universe of meaning, but by the originality of human existence in the world. (Mohammadi Vakili 2014)
- 8- The same quote from Fraser's travelogue in the book Qajar Painters and Painters by Willem Floor and Others is inadvertently quoted in the house of the King of Spring Poets, the royal poet of the mid-1830s, which is incorrect.
- 9- In Iranian architecture, Andaruni refers to the inner section where ladies dwelt. In Arabic, it's referred to as a harem.
- 10- Arkhaliq is part of both male and female traditional dress of the peoples of the Caucasus and Iran
- 11- Termeh is a type of Persian handwoven fabric made predominantly in the province of Isfahan.

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